

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION

Dr. Henry Garrett ◦ Independent Researcher ◦ Department of Mathematics ◦ DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com ◦ Manhattan, NY, USA

1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\ &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\ & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\ & \} |. \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and a Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Since there are more ways to get type results a DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, there is a need to

“re-define” the concept of “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION mastery”.
SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this
method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a DOUBLY
CONNECTED DOMINATION. If the specified table contains “values of vertices,
supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. “values of vertices & number of
positions in alphabet”, “Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”,
“values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, “super edge values&max values of its
vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples
and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass
SuperHyperGraph based on DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. This is the
original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type
would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all DOUBLY CONNECTED
DOMINATION until DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, then it is officially
called “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”, but otherwise, it is not DOUBLY
CONNECTED DOMINATION. There is some explanation for the original definition
titled “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”. These two examples are further
explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass
disciplinary methods based on a dominant DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION.
Because of having DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, there is a need to
“re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION” and
“neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”. SuperHyperVertices and
SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of
tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph.
“Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the
desired table exists, a DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION is redefined to a
“Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”. It is useful to define a
“Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain
Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED
DOMINATION becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. “Neutrosophic
SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”,
“Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and
“Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a
SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider
a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows.
It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two
given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an
intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is
SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges.
It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between
two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no
SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is
given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which
form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one
SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a
SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel
suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called
“SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel,
the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as
“SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special”

cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”.
Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree
of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called
“Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis
of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods.
Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model
(called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined
by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect,
because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects
of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be
the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what
happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and
have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and
effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be
visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find
the longest DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION or the strongest DOUBLY
CONNECTED DOMINATION in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some
general results are presented for the longest DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION
called DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and the strongest DOUBLY
CONNECTED DOMINATION called Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED
DOMINATION. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have
only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three
SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle,
but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not
form. A basic introduction to the theory of DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION
Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED}
DOMINATION, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I
try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the
established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded
in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some
groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In
embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”.
So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis
about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs”
and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of
cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and
groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us
to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes,
things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond
them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and
neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise
data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous
SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially

called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neurosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION or Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION” and “neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming

sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, are specified in the sections “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION” and “Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”. In the concept of dealing with results and in DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”, “Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [1]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by

x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a **Eulerian-Path-Cut** of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

(viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n')$; 256

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$. 257

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets. 258-267

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 268-269

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. 270-277

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. 278
279
280
281
282
283
284
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . 285
286
287
288
- On the Figure (4), there's no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 is a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 289
290
291
- On the Figure (5), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 292
293
- On the Figure (6), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 294
295
- On the Figure (7), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 296
297
- On the Figure (8), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 298
299
- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 300
301
- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 302
303

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (11), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 304
305
- On the Figure (12), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 306
307
- On the Figure (13), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 308
309
- On the Figure (14), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 310
311
- On the Figure (15), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 312
313
- On the Figure (16), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 314
315
- On the Figure (17), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 316
317
- On the Figure (18), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 318
319
- On the Figure (19), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 320
321
- On the Figure (20), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 322
323
- On the Figure (21), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 324
325
- On the Figure (22), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 326
327

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-overpacked SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

351

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$supp(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

352

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

353

354

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

355

(ii) $V = \{ (V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0 \}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

356

357

(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

358

359

(iv) $E = \{ (E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0 \}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

360

361

(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

362

(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

363

(vii) $\sum_i supp(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

364

(viii) $\sum_{i'} supp(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

365

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

366

367

368

369

370

371

372

373

374

375

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

376

377

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

378

379

380

381

(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

382

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 383
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 384
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 385
386
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 387
388
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 389
390

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities. 391
392
393

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 394
395

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable. 396
397

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. 398
399

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; 400
401
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; 402
403
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; 404
405
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 406
407
408
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 409
410
411
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 412
413
414

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion. 415
416
417

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up. 418
419
420

Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up. 421
422
423
424
425

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Example 3.19. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is up.

Example 3.20. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is up.

Definition 3.21. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_i$;

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 447
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 448
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 449
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 450
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 451
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 452
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 453
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 454
455

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 456

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 457

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 458
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 459
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 460
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 461
462

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 463
(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7). 464

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 465
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 466
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 468
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 469

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 470

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 472

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 474
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 477
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 481
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 483

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 487

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 491

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 493

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5). 518
519
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6). 520
521
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7). 522
523

4 Main Resultant 524

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION). 525
526

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds. 527
528
529
530

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

it is dominating and both D and $V(G) - D$ are connected.
 $\} |$.

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	E_1	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_2	$(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)$	E_2	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_3	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	E_3	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_4	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	V_5	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_6	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	V_7	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

it is dominating and both D and $V(G) - D$ are connected.
 $\left. \right\}$.

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9). 541
542

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 543
 Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 544
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2,4}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 545
 SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and 546
 statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria 547
 holds. 548

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

it is dominating and both D and $V(G) - D$ are connected.
 $\left. \right\}$.

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10). 549
550

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 551
 Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 552

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-4}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-5}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-6}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 4}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16).

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7,11,15,19,24,32-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 &\text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 &\} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-24,31-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 &\text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 &\} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (21).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{it is dominating and both } D \text{ and } V(G) - D \text{ are connected.} \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle don't coincide.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set is as follows.*

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} set is as follows.*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \end{array} \right\}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

is a longest SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION}. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION}. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} except from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \end{array} \right\}$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set is as follows.

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. □ 731 732 733

Proposition 5.8. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let 734

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

735

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There’s a new way to redefine as 736 737

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. □ 738 739 740

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set is as follows.* 741 742

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \\ V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \\ \} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 743

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

744

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).*

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.12. *(Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).*

- (i). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set.*
- (ii). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION set.*

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION}. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION}. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION}, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} or the Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION} in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

Figure 44. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION

Table 23. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (44), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (44) and the Table (23), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (44), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION.

9 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. The SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 9.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer's recognitions? 887
888

Question 9.2. Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION? 889
890

Question 9.3. Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them? 891
892

Question 9.4. Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION? 893
894
895

Problem 9.5. The SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperDOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, are there else? 896
897
898

Problem 9.6. Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results? 899
900

Problem 9.7. What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions? 901
902

10 Conclusion and Closing Remarks 903

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted. 904
905
906

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title "Cancer Diagnosis". To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION and Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in "cancer diagnosis" and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called "DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", based on the connections of Cancer's movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The "SuperHyper" prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (24), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

Table 24. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION	
3. Neutrosophic DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION	2. Other SuperHyperNumber
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

11 Background 907

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them. 908
909

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55. 910
911
912
913
914
915
916
917

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 918
919
920
921
922
923
924
925
926
927
928

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Recognition. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 929
930
931
932
933
934
935
936
937
938
939
940

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using 941
942
943
944
945

neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*" in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*" in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled "*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring*"

alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [288]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set

and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [289]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [290]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [291]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [294]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [295]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [298]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [301]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [302]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [303]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [304]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [305]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [306]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [317]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in **Ref. [318]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4-318], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [319-475]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [476, 477].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [476]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [477]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1-3]. The formalization of the notions on the

framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–318] alongside scientific research books at [319–475]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd, in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [476, 477].

References

1. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot”, *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03).
2. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05).
3. Henry Garrett, “A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03).
4. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04).
5. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88).
6. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124).
7. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04)
8. Henry Garrett, “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09)
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>

10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>, <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>
11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1).
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1).
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1).
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1).
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1).
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1).
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1).
19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1).

22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1195
1196
1197
1198
23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1199
1200
1201
1202
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1203
1204
1205
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1206
1207
1208
1209
1210
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1211
1212
1213
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1214
1215
1216
1217
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1218
1219
1220
1221
29. Henry Garrett, “*Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices*”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1). 1222
1223
1224
1225
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By ESTRAINED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14515147). 1226
1227
1228
31. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By ESTRAINED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14507321). 1229
1230
1231
32. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By RESTRAINED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14501230). 1232
1233
1234
33. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dom-forcing*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14477108). 1235
1236
1237
34. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dom-forcing*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14449513). 1238
1239
1240

35. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14261015). 1241-1243
36. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14031032). 1244-1246
37. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14019047). 1247-1249
38. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13957693). 1250-1252
39. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13909326). 1253-1255
40. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13893734). 1256-1258
41. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13890872). 1259-1261
42. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13834065). 1262-1264
43. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13826744). 1265-1267
44. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13823150). 1268-1270
45. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13748678). 1271-1273
46. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13629264). 1274-1276
47. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13618512). 1277-1279
48. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13457634). 1280-1282
49. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13447621). 1283-1285

50. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13386125). 1286
1287
1288
51. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359880). 1289
1290
1291
52. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359103). 1292
1293
1294
53. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13329472). 1295
1296
1297
54. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13091499). 1298
1299
1300
55. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13134329). 1301
1302
1303
56. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13218489). 1304
1305
1306
57. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786). 1307
1308
1309
58. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339). 1310
1311
1312
59. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172). 1313
1314
1315
60. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424). 1316
1317
1318
61. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758). 1319
1320
1321
62. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919). 1322
1323
1324
63. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1325
1326
1327
64. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1328
1329
1330

65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1331
1332
1333
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1334
1335
1336
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1337
1338
1339
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1340
1341
1342
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1343
1344
1345
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1346
1347
1348
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1349
1350
1351
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1352
1353
1354
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1355
1356
1357
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1358
1359
1360
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1361
1362
1363
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1364
1365
1366
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1367
1368
1369
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1370
1371
1372
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1373
1374
1375

80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1376
1377
1378
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1379
1380
1381
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1382
1383
1384
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1385
1386
1387
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1388
1389
1390
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1391
1392
1393
86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1394
1395
1396
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1397
1398
1399
1400
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1401
1402
1403
1404
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1405
1406
1407
1408
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1409
1410
1411
1412
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1413
1414
1415
1416
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1417
1418
1419
1420

93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1421
1422
1423
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1424
1425
1426
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1427
1428
1429
1430
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1431
1432
1433
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1434
1435
1436
98. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1437
1438
1439
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1440
1441
1442
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1443
1444
1445
1446
101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1447
1448
1449
1450
102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1451
1452
1453
1454
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1455
1456
1457
1458
104. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1459
1460
1461
1462
105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1463
1464
1465
1466

106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1467
1468
1469
1470
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1471
1472
1473
1474
108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1475
1476
1477
1478
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1479
1480
1481
110. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1482
1483
1484
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1485
1486
1487
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1488
1489
1490
113. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1491
1492
1493
114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1494
1495
1496
115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1497
1498
1499
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1500
1501
1502
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1503
1504
1505
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1506
1507
1508
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1509
1510
1511

120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1512
1513
1514
121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1515
1516
1517
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1518
1519
1520
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1521
1522
1523
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1524
1525
1526
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1527
1528
1529
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1530
1531
1532
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1533
1534
1535
128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1536
1537
1538
129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1539
1540
1541
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1542
1543
1544
131. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1545
1546
1547
132. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1548
1549
1550
133. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1551
1552
1553
134. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1554
1555
1556

135. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1557
1558
1559
136. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1560
1561
1562
137. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1563
1564
1565
138. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1566
1567
1568
139. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1569
1570
1571
140. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1572
1573
1574
141. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1575
1576
1577
142. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1578
1579
1580
143. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1581
1582
1583
144. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1584
1585
1586
145. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1587
1588
1589
146. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1590
1591
1592
147. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1593
1594
1595
148. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1596
1597
1598
149. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1599
1600
1601

150. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1602
1603
1604
1605
151. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1606
1607
1608
1609
152. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1610
1611
1612
153. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1613
1614
1615
154. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1616
1617
1618
155. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1619
1620
1621
156. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1622
1623
1624
157. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1625
1626
1627
158. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1628
1629
1630
159. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1631
1632
1633
160. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1634
1635
1636
161. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1637
1638
1639
162. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1640
1641
1642
163. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1643
1644
1645

164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1646
1647
1648
165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1649
1650
1651
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1652
1653
1654
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1655
1656
1657
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1658
1659
1660
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1661
1662
1663
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1664
1665
1666
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1667
1668
1669
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1670
1671
1672
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1673
1674
1675
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1676
1677
1678
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1679
1680
1681
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1682
1683
1684
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1685
1686
1687
1688

178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1689
1690
1691
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1692
1693
1694
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1695
1696
1697
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1698
1699
1700
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1701
1702
1703
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1704
1705
1706
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1707
1708
1709
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1710
1711
1712
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1713
1714
1715
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1716
1717
1718
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1719
1720
1721
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1722
1723
1724
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1725
1726
1727
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1728
1729
1730
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1731
1732
1733

193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1734
1735
1736
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1737
1738
1739
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1740
1741
1742
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1743
1744
1745
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1746
1747
1748
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1749
1750
1751
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1752
1753
1754
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1755
1756
1757
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1758
1759
1760
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1761
1762
1763
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1764
1765
1766
204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1767
1768
1769
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1770
1771
1772
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1773
1774
1775
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1776
1777
1778

208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1779
1780
1781
209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1782
1783
1784
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1785
1786
1787
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1788
1789
1790
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1791
1792
1793
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1794
1795
1796
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1797
1798
1799
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1800
1801
1802
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1803
1804
1805
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1806
1807
1808
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1809
1810
1811
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1812
1813
1814
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1815
1816
1817
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1818
1819
1820
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1821
1822
1823

223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1824
1825
1826
224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1827
1828
1829
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1830
1831
1832
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1833
1834
1835
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1836
1837
1838
228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1839
1840
1841
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1842
1843
1844
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1845
1846
1847
231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1848
1849
1850
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1851
1852
1853
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1854
1855
1856
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1857
1858
1859
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1860
1861
1862
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1863
1864
1865
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1866
1867
1868

238. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1869
1870
1871
239. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1872
1873
1874
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1875
1876
1877
241. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1878
1879
1880
242. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1881
1882
1883
243. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1884
1885
1886
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1887
1888
1889
245. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1890
1891
1892
246. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1893
1894
1895
247. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1896
1897
1898
248. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1899
1900
1901
249. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1902
1903
1904
250. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1905
1906
1907
251. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1908
1909
1910
252. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1911
1912
1913

253. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1914
1915
1916
254. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1917
1918
1919
255. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1920
1921
1922
256. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1923
1924
1925
257. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1926
1927
1928
258. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1929
1930
1931
259. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1932
1933
1934
260. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1935
1936
1937
261. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1938
1939
1940
262. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1941
1942
1943
263. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1944
1945
1946
264. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1947
1948
1949
265. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1950
1951
1952
1953
266. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1954
1955
1956
1957

267. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1958
1959
1960
1961
268. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1962
1963
1964
1965
269. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1966
1967
1968
1969
270. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1970
1971
1972
1973
271. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1974
1975
1976
1977
272. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1978
1979
1980
273. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 1981
1982
1983
274. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 1984
1985
1986
275. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 1987
1988
1989
1990
276. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 1991
1992
1993
1994
277. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 1995
1996
1997
1998
1999
278. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 2000
2001
2002
2003
2004

279. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 2005
2006
2007
2008
280. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 2009
2010
2011
281. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 2012
2013
2014
2015
282. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 2016
2017
2018
2019
283. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 2020
2021
2022
284. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 2023
2024
2025
2026
2027
2028
285. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 2029
2030
2031
2032
286. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 2033
2034
2035
2036
287. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 2037
2038
2039
2040
288. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 2041
2042
2043
289. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 2044
2045
2046
2047
290. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2048
2049
2050
2051

291. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 2052
2053
2054
2055
292. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2056
2057
2058
2059
293. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2060
2061
2062
294. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 2063
2064
2065
295. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 2066
2067
2068
2069
296. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2070
2071
2072
2073
297. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 2074
2075
2076
2077
298. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 2078
2079
2080
2081
299. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 2082
2083
2084
300. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 2085
2086
2087
301. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 2088
2089
2090
302. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 2091
2092
2093
303. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2094
2095
2096

304. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2097
2098
2099
2100
305. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2101
2102
2103
306. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2104
2105
2106
2107
307. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2108
2109
2110
308. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2111
2112
2113
309. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2114
2115
2116
2117
2118
310. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2119
2120
2121
2122
2123
311. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2124
2125
2126
312. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2127
2128
2129
313. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2130
2131
2132
2133
314. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2134
2135
2136
2137
315. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2138
2139
2140
2141

316. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966).
2142
2143
2144
2145
317. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244).
2146
2147
2148
318. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160).
2149
2150
2151
2152
319. Henry Garrett, “RESTRAINED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14497269).
2153
2154
320. Henry Garrett, “Dom-forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14175736).
2155
2156
321. Henry Garrett, “Diamond search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13600433).
2157
2158
322. Henry Garrett, “Triangle-free search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13594674).
2159
2160
323. Henry Garrett, “Diamond search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13525750).
2161
2162
324. Henry Garrett, “Triangle-free search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13512157).
2163
2164
325. Henry Garrett, “Edge Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13376543).
2165
2166
326. Henry Garrett, “Vertex Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13294466).
2167
2168
327. Henry Garrett, “Burning Number In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12797511).
2169
2170
328. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570).
2171
2172
329. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785).
2173
2174
330. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087).
2175
2176
331. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996).
2177
2178
332. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821).
2179
2180
333. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118).
2181
2182

- 334. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2183
2184
- 335. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2185
2186
- 336. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2187
2188
- 337. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2189
2190
- 338. Henry Garrett, “Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2191
2192
- 339. Henry Garrett, “Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2193
2194
- 340. Henry Garrett, “Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2195
2196
- 341. Henry Garrett, “Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2197
2198
- 342. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2199
2200
- 343. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2201
2202
- 344. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2203
2204
- 345. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2205
2206
- 346. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2207
2208
- 347. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2209
2210
- 348. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2211
2212
- 349. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2213
2214
- 350. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2215
2216
- 351. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2217
2218
- 352. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2219
2220
- 353. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2221
2222

- 354. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2223
2224
- 355. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2225
2226
- 356. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2227
2228
- 357. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2229
2230
- 358. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2231
2232
- 359. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2233
2234
- 360. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2235
2236
- 361. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2237
2238
- 362. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2239
2240
- 363. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2241
2242
- 364. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2243
2244
- 365. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2245
2246
- 366. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2247
2248
- 367. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2249
2250
- 368. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2251
2252
- 369. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2253
2254
- 370. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2255
2256
- 371. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2257
2258
- 372. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2259
2260
- 373. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2261
2262

374. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2263
2264
375. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2265
2266
376. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2267
2268
377. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2269
2270
378. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2271
2272
379. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2273
2274
380. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2275
2276
381. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2277
2278
382. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2279
2280
383. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2281
2282
384. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2283
2284
385. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2285
2286
386. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2287
2288
387. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2289
2290
388. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2291
2292
389. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2293
2294
390. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2295
2296
391. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2297
2298
392. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2299
2300
393. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2301
2302

394. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2303
2304
395. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2305
2306
396. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2307
2308
397. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2309
2310
398. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2311
2312
399. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2313
2314
400. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2315
2316
401. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2317
2318
402. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2319
2320
403. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2321
2322
404. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2323
2324
405. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2325
2326
406. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2327
2328
407. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2329
2330
408. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2331
2332
409. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2333
2334
410. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2335
2336
411. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2337
2338
412. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2339
2340
413. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2341
2342

414. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2343
2344
415. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2345
2346
416. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2347
2348
417. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2349
2350
418. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2351
2352
419. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2353
2354
420. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2355
2356
421. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2357
2358
422. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2359
2360
423. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2361
2362
424. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2363
2364
425. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2365
2366
426. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2367
2368
427. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2369
2370
428. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2371
2372
429. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2373
2374
430. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2375
2376
431. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2377
2378
432. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2379
2380
433. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2381
2382

434. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2383
2384
435. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2385
2386
436. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2387
2388
437. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2389
2390
438. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2391
2392
439. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2393
2394
440. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2395
2396
441. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2397
2398
442. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2399
2400
443. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2401
2402
444. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2403
2404
445. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2405
2406
446. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2407
2408
447. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2409
2410
448. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2411
2412
449. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2413
2414
450. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2415
2416
451. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2417
2418
452. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2419
2420
453. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2421
2422

454. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2423
2424
455. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2425
2426
456. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2427
2428
457. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2429
2430
458. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2431
2432
459. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2433
2434
460. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2435
2436
461. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2437
2438
462. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2439
2440
463. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2441
2442
464. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2443
2444
465. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2445
2446
466. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2447
2448
467. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2449
2450
468. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2451
2452
469. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2453
2454
470. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2455
2456
471. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2457
2458
472. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2459
2460
473. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2461
2462

474. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2463
10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2464
475. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2465
10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2466
476. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2467
10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2468
477. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2469
10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2470